

Secure Repository for Documents

{source:<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1IW5r5f9CIYLChv4p82tQ9j7JOIjyCuVD8EzFNI2F21qw/edit> }

Background

Documents (including guidance documents and fact sheets) are currently held in a folder in the CEDA pages of the DDC. This is not ideal, as the documents need to be moved when the site is reorganised, and they are not easily discovered by users making generic searches for information. Placing documents in well managed online repositories increases long term security and also provides greater visibility. The appearance of these documents on DDC web pages will be virtually unchanged.

A specific proposal: Zenodo

zenodo.org is a repository run by CERN. It was developed within the European consortium project OpenAIRE and one of the proof-of-concept projects for the European Open Science Cloud. It has the hardware and informatics resources of CERN behind it and a consortium committed to building a service for the entire scientific community.

Zenodo provides a “community” feature, which allows a group of people to create a moderated collection of documents within Zenodo. For example, the European Human Brain Project has its own Zenodo community¹. We can create an “IPCC DDC” community within Zenodo, so that the collection of documents will be visible as a group to users who approach it through the Zenodo search.

Additional benefits

- Each document (or collection of documents) deposited in Zenodo will be assigned a DataCite DOI;
- Zenodo can manage multiple versions of a document: each new document gets a new DOI, but there is also a DOI to refer to the expanding collection of versioned documents.

For example, [10.5281/zenodo.774088](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.774088) is the top level DOI for the CMIP6 Data Request, it always resolves to the latest version (currently [10.5281/zenodo.820430](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.820430)).

¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/hbp/search?page=1&size=20&q=>

Document Categories

- Guidelines
- Fact sheets
- Dataset Assessments: questionnaire and assessment bundled into one Zenodo dataset
- Portal Assessments
- Process Documents: process for guidelines, dataset assessment etc.
- Technical Documentation.